

Synthesis of Possible Antiamebic Agents

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The antiamebic activity of 5-chloro-7-iodo-8-hydroxyquinoline and 5,7-diiodo-8-hydroxyquinoline is well-known. Since their discovery a large number of halohydroxyquinolines, both iodinated and non-iodinated, have been prepared^{1,2}. Some of them displayed encouraging antiamebic activity. Two such compounds, viz. 2-diethylaminoethyl-3-n-propyl-4-chloro-5-(or 7)-iodo-8-hydroxyquinoline and 2-dimethylaminoethyl-3-n-propyl-5-chloro-7-iodo-8-hydroxyquinoline were found promising³. The antiamebic activity of the halogenated 8-hydroxyquinolines is believed to be due to chelation of Fe^{2+} ion¹, which is necessary for the amebal growth. Halogens, in this moiety, play a secondary role in enhancing the acid dissociation constant of the ligand. Higher *in vitro* amebicidal activity of the above compounds³ might be due to the introduction of an extra chelating centre, viz. the dialkylaminoethyl group in the 8-hydroxyquinoline moiety, which is expected to increase the stability of the chelates as well as reduce the Fe^{2+} -ligand ratio.

It is logical then to consider the compounds (like **3** and **4**) with more than one chelating centre in a molecule, and with halogens too, in the same relative positions as in iodochloro-hydroxyquinoline; and which should yield potent amebicidal agents. The present design of possible amebicidal compounds, is based on this idea. In this connection, it is noteworthy to mention that quinoxaline-1,4-dioxide was effective against experimental amebic infection⁴ in animals, but clinical trial precluded further use, for the toxic side-effects.

The present compounds have been synthesised as shown below :

3; X = H or I **4**; R = H or Cl, X = Br or I

1,4-Dimethoxybenzene has been nitrated with fuming nitric acid to give a mixture of 2,3- and 2,5-dinitro compounds. The mixture was

separated into two isomers, in pure form, by chromatographic method over neutral alumina, in a very small quantity, rendering the method ineffective. Fractional crystallisation of the mixture, from ethyl acetate, gave mainly 2,3-dinitro-1,4-dimethoxybenzene which was reduced to the respective amine, and subsequently reacted with diacetyl, to produce 2,3-dimethyl-5,8-dimethoxyquinoxaline, which was separated in pure form and good yield by column chromatography over neutral alumina. The methoxy compounds were demethylated by refluxing with 40% hydrobromic acid. The resulting hydroxy compounds have been iodinated or brominated.

Pharmacology : Curiously enough, none of the compounds (**3** and **4**) were found to exhibit *in vitro*, amebicidal activity upto a concentration of 1000 mcg/ml (for iodochlorohydroxyquinoline, it is 100 mcg/ml). The geometry of the compounds **3** and **4** is such that both the chelating centres of one molecule of ligand cannot enter into coordination sphere of one Fe^{2+} ion due to the steric factor, but the other chelation centre of the same ligand molecule is free to enter into the coordination sphere of another Fe^{2+} ion, and thus may reduce Fe^{2+} ion in a higher proportion compared to iodochlorohydroxyquinoline. These compounds thus have been expected to exhibit higher, or at least equal amebicidal activity as iodochloro-hydroxyquinoline. But the results were reverse. So, the amebicidal activity of the halogenated 8-hydroxyquinolines might not be only for their chelation property; there are other reasons. The statement is further substantiated by the fact that 5,7-dibromo-8-hydroxyquinoline benzoate ester is effective against amebiasis¹ and the moiety is devoid of any chelation facility.

Experimental

2,3-Dimethyl-6,7-diiodo-5,8-dihydroxyquinoxaline (3; X = I) : A solution of 2,3-dimethyl-5,8-dihydroxyquinoxaline (0.1 g) in chloroform (10 ml) was added to a solution of iodine monochloride (0.18 g) in chloroform (10 ml). After 10 min chloroform was evaporated and the resulting solid

was washed with 10% HCl and 1% sodium hydrosulphite and crystallised from chloroform, m.p. 95° (Found : I, 56.97. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_8\text{O}_2\text{N}_2\text{I}_2$ calcd. for : I, 57.46%).

1,6-Dimethoxy-4,9-dichlorophenazine : A mixture of 2-nitro-4-chloroanisole (28 g), 2-amino-4-chloroanisole (16 g), finely powdered KOH (30 g) and toluene (200 ml) was refluxed with stirring in an oil-bath (158°), for 6 h. The resulting mass was filtered, extracted with 15% HCl and the acid extract was neutralised with ammonia (33%). The resulting solid was dried and then extracted out in the pure form by continuous hot extraction in a Soxhlet apparatus with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°). Removal of the solvent, gave a yellow crystalline solid (6.5 g), m.p. 82° (Found : C, 54; H, 3; N, 9.11. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{Cl}_2\text{O}_2$ calcd. for : C, 54.37; H, 3.23; N, 9.06%); nmr δ (CDCl_3 ; TMS) 3.3 (4H, s, ArH), 6.2 (6H, s, OCH_3).

1,6-Dihydroxy-4,9-dichlorophenazine (4; R = Cl, X = H) : A mixture of 1,6-dimethoxy-4,9-dichlorophenazine (0.5 g) and HBr acid (40%; 10 ml) was refluxed for 20 h. The cooled neutralised mass was then extracted with chloroform, purified chromatographically over silica gel with benzene as an eluent and the resulting solid was crystallised from CCl_4 , (0.2 g), m.p. 130–32° (Found : N, 9.95. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_6\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{Cl}_2$ calcd. for : N, 10%); ν_{max} (nujol) 3 340-3 405 cm^{-1} (OH).

1,6-Dihydroxy-2,7-dibromo-4,9-dichlorophenazine (4; R = Cl, X = Br) : A solution of 1,6-dihydroxy-4,9-dichlorophenazine (0.2 g) in CCl_4 (10 ml) was added to a solution of bromine (0.6 g) in CCl_4 (10 ml). The mass was then triturated with sodium bicarbonate solution, filtered, and resulting solid was washed with water, dried and crystallised from CCl_4 , (0.15 g), m.p. 239–42°d, (Found : N, 5.93. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_4\text{N}_2\text{O}_2\text{Cl}_2\text{Br}_2$ calcd. for : N, 6.38%); ν_{max} (KBr) 3 425 cm^{-1} (OH).

1,6-Dihydroxy-2,7-diiodo-4,9-dichlorophenazine (4; R = Cl, X = I) : A solution of 1,6-dihydroxy-4,9-dichlorophenazine (0.2 g) in HCl (15%; 10

NOTE

ml) was added to a solution of ICl in concentrated HCl (2 ml). The resulting solid was washed with 5% HCl and water, dried and crystallised from alcohol, (0.1 g), m.p. 106–08°d, yield 0.1 g (Found : I, 47. C₁₂H₄N₂Cl₂I₂ calcd. for : I, 47.65%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 450 cm⁻¹ (OH).

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